

Primary gas standards for the determination of sulfur-based impurities at trace level in hydrogen

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogen fuel quality needs to comply with ISO 14687:2025 to avoid harmful impact on applications using proton-exchange membrane (PEM) fuel cells. For total sulfur as one of the most impactful contaminants, an amount fraction of 4 nmol/mol has been set as threshold (so-called Grade D quality). In this study, novel gaseous primary gas standards (PGS) of seven sulfur compounds were prepared either gravimetrically at 1000 nmol/mol, 100 nmol/mol, and 10 nmol/mol, or dynamically diluted down to 4 nmol/mol in hydrogen and argon matrices with relative expanded uncertainties well below 10 % ($k = 2$) and proven stability of at least 9–12 months. Two different cylinder passivation treatments were compared, with one treatment identified as unsuitable since reactions took place within the mixture. By performing a cross-check study, equivalence between both sets of PGS could be demonstrated (≤ 5 % relative deviation for most of the sulfur species).

1. Introduction

Global population growth has boosted economic development and expanded civilization, thus increasing the demand for energy. Meeting this demand has become one of today's most urgent global challenges, as it affects both prosperity and environmental sustainability [1]. Historically, fossil fuels have been the primary driver of economic expansion and industrialization, constituting around 88 % of the energy sources used in industries [2]. The utilization of hydrogen as a sustainable energy carrier offers significant potential to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and diminish harmful air pollutants generated by the transportation sector. It is considered a key enabler of the global energy transition and may account for up to 32 % of the fuel demand by 2050 [3,4]. Nevertheless, a major challenge that may hinder the widespread adoption of hydrogen-powered mobility lies in the stringent hydrogen fuel-quality specifications stipulated by European legislation [5].

The fuel cell system in a hydrogen vehicle requires hydrogen of very high-quality as even trace levels of impurities can adversely affect fuel cell performance and lifetime [6–8]. Sulfur is one of the most impactful contaminants in hydrogen for fuel cells [9,10]. Sulfur-containing compounds can, e.g., be residues from natural gas, from which hydrogen is produced in the steam reforming process [11]. Therefore, the

international standard ISO 14687 [12] specifies a threshold of 4 nmol/mol for the total amount fraction of sulfur for PEM fuel cell electric vehicles (FCV) applications ('Grade D' quality). The determination of the amount fraction of all sulfurous compounds in hydrogen is usually carried out by gas chromatography equipped with a sulfur chemiluminescence detector (GC/SCD) [13–17]. This detector is specific for sulfur and has the advantage that in first approximation it counts the sulfur atoms in a gas sample. This particular analytical instrumentation requires calibration standards to obtain accurate measurement results, which in turn are necessary for ensuring quality and safety of applications requiring hydrogen fuel. For instrument calibration, measurement standards with metrological traceability, such as primary gas standards (PGS), are required [18,19].

This study demonstrates the feasibility of preparing stable PGS with low uncertainties containing trace levels of sulfur compounds for the determination of hydrogen quality. VSL, the National Metrology Institute of the Netherlands, and BAM, the Designated Institute maintaining and providing the German National Standards of gas composition for calorific value determination (energy gases) and surveillance of vehicle exhaust emission, have independently prepared gas mixtures containing a selection of seven sulfur species in high-pressure cylinders, according to ISO 6142-1 [20], with amount fractions of 1000 nmol/mol, 100

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nmol/mol, and 10 nmol/mol. Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), carbonyl sulfide (COS), methyl mercaptan (MeSH), ethyl mercaptan (EtSH), dimethyl sulfide (DMS), diethyl sulfide (DES), and tetrahydrothiophene (THT) were selected as target components. VSL resorted to hydrogen as matrix gas throughout, whereas BAM used both argon and hydrogen. To obtain measurement standards at the threshold level of 4 nmol/mol, the reference materials were dynamically diluted with pure hydrogen, respectively argon, by means of thermal mass flow controllers (MFC) according to ISO 6145-7 [21]. The study was complemented by a cross-validation between gas standards of both institutes and a stability study of the prepared PGS.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

For the preparation of the gravimetric PGS, dynamic dilutions and subsequent analyses, the chemical compounds listed in Table S1 in the supplementary material were used. Chemicals used for reference materials require high nominal purity (here, better than 99 % for the sulfur compounds and 99.9999 % (or 6.0) for hydrogen and argon, respectively). As COS and MeSH could not be obtained with suitable purity in Germany at the time, VSL provided BAM with binary mixtures in argon. These mixtures were prepared in accordance with ISO 6142-1 [20]. The purity of each sulfur compound and dilution gas was checked according to ISO 19229 [22]. At VSL, binary gas mixtures with nominal amount fraction of 1000 μmol/mol were prepared for all the sulfur chemicals. Impurities, such as other accompanying sulfur compounds, were identified by Gas Chromatography (GC) with Mass Spectrometer Detector and quantified by GC with Sulfur Chemiluminescence Detector (SCD). The latter is sulfur-specific and has equimolar response for sulfur atoms.

Apart from COS and MeSH, for which purity data was available from VSL, BAM referred to the certificates of analysis for the respective batch provided by the chemicals manufacturer.

2.2. Preparation of gravimetric primary gas standards (PGS)

2.2.1. General

In accordance with ISO 6142-1 [20], BAM and VSL have independently prepared PGS containing a) all seven sulfur substances, and b) H₂S as a binary mixture. Both had amount fractions of 1000 nmol/mol and 100 nmol/mol. VSL additionally prepared gravimetric mixtures at the 10 nmol/mol level. The PGS were prepared in hydrogen (VSL) and argon (BAM) in aluminum gas cylinders (Luxfer, UK) of 5 L (VSL) and 10 L (BAM) water volume. The use of argon can be beneficial since fewer dilution steps are required due to the higher molar mass of argon. To avoid adsorption of molecules onto cylinder walls or valves as well as catalytically induced chemical reactions with these materials, the inner surfaces have been specially treated with a proprietary procedure by Air Liquide (Alpha Tech®) intended for passivation. Benesch et al. reported that this treatment is effective at least for H₂S at amount fractions of 100 nmol/mol [23]. Based on own experience, this surface treatment has proven to be also effective for other sulfur components. In addition, VSL prepared another set of gas mixtures at 100 nmol/mol and 10 nmol/mol with the same nominal composition in 5 L aluminum cylinders with a proprietary treatment provided by EffecTech (DB Gold). This was done to evaluate the effect of another cylinder type and surface passivation method on the stability of the gas standards.

2.2.2. Preconditioning of cylinders

Each new cylinder was cleaned by repeated flushing with dry, high-purity nitrogen followed by evacuating it to a pressure between 5·10⁻⁷ mbar and 5·10⁻⁶ mbar. In addition, BAM pre-conditioned their cylinders by filling them with the target chemicals at approximately the target concentration. The intention of this procedure is to saturate the inner surfaces of the container with the target components for the first time.

This mixture is charged with the corresponding matrix gas to a pressure of about 10 bar and then left remaining at these conditions for at least 24 h. A portion of it is then transferred to the following cylinder of the dilution series and further diluted with matrix gas. That process was continued with each cylinder until the final dilution point. Before the 'real' filling, the cylinders were evacuated again.

The detailed filling procedures are explained in the following sections.

The PGS in the Alpha Tech® cylinders were prepared in duplicate, so that one set could be sent to the other institute for the cross-check validation (section 2.7).

2.2.3. Preparation of PGS in argon at BAM

Fig. 1 schematically displays the preparation steps of both H₂S, as binary mixture, and the multi-component mixture containing all seven sulfur species in an argon matrix. The first row of the boxes displays the cylinder number with the exact filling date after the hyphen (syntax: 1234-yyymmdd). The numbers in circles indicate the order of filling for the preparation of the multi-component mixture, where the components were consecutively injected in ascending order of their vapor pressure to ensure that no back diffusion could take place. For better readability, the letters AA to DD assigned to the mixtures in the figure are used in the following instead of the cylinder numbers. The filling plans including all details on the calculated masses and final cylinder pressures can be found in Fig. S1 and S2 of the supplementary material.

Binary premixtures of H₂S, COS and MeSH in argon were prepared from the pure substances by filling them into the cylinder followed by weighing with a robot (KUKA KR 70 R2100) coupled to a high-resolution mass comparator (Sartorius MCM40K3, range: 0–41 kg, readability: 1 mg) to determine the mass of each gas portion. Finally, the matrix gas was added bringing the cylinder to pressures usually between 120 bar and 150 bar. The following steps were carried out as depicted in Fig. 1. For the multi-component mixture (AA), the four liquid compounds THT, DES, DMS and EtSH were consecutively injected with gas-tight microliter syringes (Hamilton®, maximum volume 250 μL). Before and after filling, the syringes were weighed with a high-resolution comparator (Sartorius CCE2004, range: 0–2500 g, readability: 0.1 mg) to determine the injected mass. Once the liquid compounds were injected into the cylinder, the COS followed by the EtSH binary pre-mixtures were introduced. With this step, residues of the liquids that still might be remaining inside or attached to the surfaces of the supply line were purged into the recipient cylinder. Ultimately, the matrix gas argon was introduced.

The binary H₂S mixture (CC) was prepared via two dilution steps from the same 2500 μmol/mol pre-mixture. The mixtures of 100 nmol/mol (BB and DD) were prepared by dilution of the gravimetric standards AA and CC. For the stability assessment, another set of multi-component gas standards of 1000 nmol/mol and 100 nmol/mol was prepared in 2025, this time in hydrogen. The detailed filling plan is displayed in Fig. S3, the final composition of the prepared gas mixtures, including the impurities, are given in Table S2 and S3 of the supplementary information.

2.2.4. Preparation of mixtures in hydrogen at VSL

Fig. 2 shows the gas standards preparation scheme at VSL.

In 2024, binary mixtures at 1 cmol/mol in H₂ were prepared from those pure sulfur compounds which are in gas phase at ambient conditions (i.e., H₂S, COS, MeSH). For the sulfur compounds in liquid phase at ambient conditions (i.e., EtSH, DMS, DES, THT), the syringe method was used to prepare gas mixtures at 1000 μmol/mol level. The H₂S binary mixture was then further diluted in several steps to obtain the final target mixtures at 1000 nmol/mol (mixtures L, M) and 100 nmol/mol (mixtures P, Q, R, S), while, for the multi-component mixtures, all binary mixtures were diluted down to 10 μmol/mol and then combined to obtain the target lower amount fractions of 1000 nmol/mol (mixtures A, B, C, X), 100 nmol/mol (mixtures D, E, F) and 10 nmol/mol (mixtures G,

Fig. 1. Gravimetric preparation at BAM – sulfur compounds in argon.

H) (Fig. 2). The compositions of the prepared gas mixtures, including the impurities, are given in Table S4 of the supplementary information. More details of the preparation method and calculations carried out at VSL are given elsewhere [24–26].

THT was included in the mixture preparation, but its results were deemed unreliable and therefore not included in the work.

2.3. Preparation of dynamic primary gas standards

In this study, the amount fraction range of 0.5 to 10 nmol/mol was targeted to cover the 4 nmol/mol threshold for the amount fraction of total sulfur as stipulated by ISO 14687 [12]. The gravimetrically produced PGS were dynamically diluted to lower amount fractions by mixing known flows of the PGS with known flows of dilution gas (pure hydrogen or argon). VSL developed a software-controlled dynamic dilution system enabling a one-stage dilution (1:100 dilution ratio) and two-stage dilution (1:10000 ratio), respectively, using thermal mass-flow controllers (MFCs) (Bronkhorst® EL-FLOW Prestige) and pressure controllers (Bronkhorst® EL-PRESS) suitable for hydrogen gas. BAM employed a similar but simplified one-stage dilution set-up, also based on thermal MFCs (Bronkhorst® EL-FLOW Prestige). In both set-ups (Fig. 3) all wetted parts, tubing, connectors, valves, and MFCs, were made of stainless steel and coated with SilcoNert2000® (SilcoTek® Coatings) to limit adsorption on contact surfaces and potential chemical reactions. In addition, all MFCs were calibrated against primary flow calibrators [BAM: Molbloc-L Laminar Flow Element, (Fluke®); VSL: mercury-sealed piston prover (Bronkhorst)] in volume rates with the respective pure matrix gas and for mixes of them at specific temperature (293.15 K) and pressure (from atmospheric to 1 MPa) conditions. Typical flow rates used for dilution are indicated in Table 5. It should be noted that these thermal MFCs use the heat capacity of the gas to control their mass flow rate. Because hydrogen and argon have significantly different heat capacities, the MFCs need specific calibration in case these gases are used both separately and mixed.

At VSL, the PGS in hydrogen at 1000 nmol/mol were used as starting mixture for the dilution. The 100 nmol/mol amount fraction was obtained by one-stage dilution by mixing the gas mixture (F1 analyte 1) with pure hydrogen (F1 H₂), while the range 0.5 to 10 nmol/mol was achieved by further diluting a small part of the gas mixture produced

from one-stage (F2 analyte) with pure hydrogen (F2 H₂) using the two-stage dilution.

BAM diluted the 100 nmol/mol PGS in pure argon.

The amount fraction $x_{i,dil2}$ in the two-stage dilution (VSL) and $x_{i,dil1}$ in the one-stage set-up (BAM and VSL) was determined using equations (1) and (2), respectively, where $x_{i,prep}$ denotes the amount fraction of component i in the gravimetrically prepared PGS assuming the dilution gas did not contain sulfurous components. The volume flow rates are given as q for each MFC [analyte (anal)/dilution (dil)]. The compression factors of the gravimetrically prepared gas mixture (Z_i) and the dilution gas (Z_{dil}) are assumed to be equal. The mixing factor (f_s) is assumed to be equal to 1 [27].

$$x_{i,dil2} = x_{i,prep} \cdot \frac{q_{anal,F1}}{q_{anal,F1} + q_{dil,F1}} \cdot \frac{q_{anal,F2}}{q_{anal,F2} + q_{dil,F2}} \cdot \frac{Z_{dil}}{Z_i \cdot f_s} \quad (1)$$

$$x_{i,dil1} = x_{i,prep} \cdot \frac{q_{anal,F1}}{q_{anal,F1} + q_{dil,F1}} \cdot \frac{Z_{dil}}{Z_i \cdot f_s} \quad (2)$$

Assuming that $Z_i = Z_{dil}$ rests on the idea that for the very diluted mixtures of the sulfurous compounds in hydrogen (argon), the compressibility factor at the same temperature and pressure is in good approximation equal to that of pure hydrogen (argon). The unit mixing factor is motivated by the fact that the calibration gas mixture is very diluted and exhibits ideal mixing behavior. In the case of diluting a gas standard with a different matrix gas, the difference in the compressibility factors (0.14 % relative between argon and hydrogen) is accounted for by using the appropriate calibration of the MFC.

2.4. Verification of the standards

2.4.1. Analysis

All measurements for the verification of the gas standards, including the cross-check validation, have been carried out using gas chromatography with sulfur chemiluminescence detector (GC/SCD). A thermal desorber (TD) was connected to the GC and it was used to preconcentrate the analytes. A TD consists of a specially designed sorbent trap able to adsorb (in this context) sulfur molecules at low temperature (−30 °C) by means of Peltier cooling, thereby concentrating the sample. A rapid heat up of the trap up to about 200 to 250 °C allows immediate

Fig. 2. Gravimetric preparation at VSL – sulfur compounds in H₂. Gas mixtures with asterisk (*) indicate cylinders with the ‘DB Gold’ treatment. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

desorption and injection into the column of the GC. With this accumulating technique, large “known” volumes of gas can be sampled on the trap. The SCD detector has the advantage of being selective towards molecules that contain at least one sulfur atom. It burns the sulfur compounds under a reducing atmosphere (with hydrogen). A chemiluminescent reaction between the combustion products and ozone follows, and the resulting emission is measured by a photomultiplier tube [28].

Thermal desorbers and gas chromatographs from two different manufacturers [BAM: PerkinElmer® Clarus 690 (GC) and PerkinElmer® ATD TurboMatrix (TD); VSL: Agilent Technologies 8890 (GC) and Markes™ Unity xr (TD)] equipped with SCD from the same manufacturer (SeNse, PAC L. P.) were used. VSL also made use of a 16-port position valve (VICI®) embedded in the GC and of a 14-channels CIA Advantage sampling system (Markes™) coupled to the TD for the automated measurement of several gas mixtures in the μmol/mol and nmol/mol range, respectively. The Clarus 690 and ATD TurboMatrix (PerkinElmer®) each have one sampling port. To control the sampling

flow and the total volume trapped into the sorbent trap of the TD, an MFC is in place. As for the dynamic dilution system, the MFC of the Markes™ TD was properly calibrated to the matrix gas used. However, the TurboMatrix TD is equipped with an MFC (Brooks® Instrument) which was calibrated to air by default, and it was not possible to carry out an argon or hydrogen calibration during the investigations.

All flow paths of the analytical system in contact with the sample were coated with SilcoNert2000® (SilcoTek®). Samples of gas mixtures with amount fractions for the sulfur components below 100 nmol/mol were either taken directly from the gas cylinder or from the dynamic dilution system (section 2.3) onto the sorbent trap. Samples of amount fractions at 100 nmol/mol and 1000 nmol/mol were sampled via the GC's sample loop [250 μL (PerkinElmer) or 1000 μL (Agilent)] and directly injected into the GC/SCD system (bypassing the TD system). Details on the temperature programs and instrument settings can be found in Table S5 in the supplementary information.

Fig. 3. Technical drawing of both employed dynamic dilution systems to achieve the sulfurs' target range of 0.5 to 100 nmol/mol and below: (a) VSL's set-up bases on mass flow controllers (MFCs) and pressure controllers (PCs) and can be operated for one- and two-stage dilutions. (b) BAM's set-up employs two MFCs for one-stage dilutions.

2.4.2. Matrix effects and linearity

As the gravimetric standards in this study have been prepared in different matrices (hydrogen and argon) the consideration of potential matrix effects on the analysis is relevant. The matrices interact differently with the GC carrier gas and the column stationary phase, thereby influencing the response, peak shape, and retention time of the sulfurs. It was checked whether matrix effects were existing and whether they influenced the measurement.

The SCD detector should be providing a linear response over a broad measurement range. To prove linearity around the threshold level, 4 dynamically prepared calibration standards were used to cover the measurement range of 0.5 to 10 nmol/mol and each standard was measured at least 4 times to be able to calculate the scattering of the instrument response. The arithmetic average and the standard deviation were calculated. The analysis of residuals according to ISO 6143 [29] was used to get information on the goodness-of-fit of the calibration.

2.4.3. Analytical precision

The analytical measurement precision was calculated for each compound from: 1) the repeatability relative standard deviation ($s_{r,i}$) of 6 to 8 consecutive measurements of the gas mixtures on the GC/SCD or TD-GC/SCD, 2) the daily measurement variation ($s_{A,i}$), and 3) the reproducibility relative standard deviation ($s_{R,i}$). $s_{R,i}$ is a combination of the repeatability ($s_{r,i}$) and the daily variation of the measurements [30] and denotes the analytical precision. The calculation of $s_{A,i}$ and $s_{R,i}$ was based on 2 to 3 series of measurements, each of them carried out on different days of the week with at least one day between the measurement days.

2.5. Assessment of consistency of preparation, accuracy, and stability of the gravimetric gas mixtures

The consistency of preparation of VSL's gravimetric sulfur compounds gas standards at each prepared amount fraction was checked by

comparing identical gas mixtures prepared in the same period and calculating the relative deviation between the maximum ($RF_{MAX,i}$) and minimum ($RF_{MIN,i}$) response factors. The compound specific RF (RF_i) of the gas mixture was determined as the ratio of the compound average measured peak area (A_i) and its corresponding amount fraction (x_i) in the gas mixture as reported in equation (3).

$$RF_i = \frac{A_i}{x_i} \quad (3)$$

The accuracy of the preparation was investigated by comparison against other gravimetric standards or against dynamically diluted gas standards. VSL has long-term experience and holds an accreditation for sulfur gas standards in methane at $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ levels. Therefore, the accuracy testing of the multi-sulfurs at 1000 nmol/mol was performed against a set of these previously characterized standards in the range 1000 nmol/mol-2500 nmol/mol using a generalized distance regression, as described in ISO 6143 [29], for the quantification of the measured values. Similarly, the H_2S binary mixtures at 1000 nmol/mol were compared against a set of earlier prepared (2019 to 2022) H_2S gas standards in the range 500-2500 nmol/mol in hydrogen. For the other standards, at 100 nmol/mol and 10 nmol/mol, the measured values $x_{i,obs}$ and relative deviations of these values from the gravimetric values ($\Delta_{rel,i}$) were obtained by direct comparison against the dynamic dilution gas standards at the same amount fractions ($x_{i,ref}$), as indicated in equations (4) and (5).

$$x_{i,obs} = \frac{A_i}{A_{i,ref}} \cdot x_{i,ref} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta_{rel,i} = \frac{x_{i,obs} - x_i}{x_i} \quad (5)$$

The value $x_{i,obs}$ is the measured (observed) amount fraction of each compound of the gravimetric gas mixture under verification. A_i and x_i are the compound average response (peak area) and its amount fraction in the gravimetric gas mixture under measurement. $A_{i,ref}$ and $x_{i,ref}$ are the compound average response (peak area) and the amount fraction of the reference gas standard. For accuracy determination, the reference gas standard was a dynamically diluted standard or a previously characterized standard. For stability calculations, a freshly prepared gravimetric standard, identical to the one under study, was used as reference standard (e.g. for the multi-component mixture at 1000 nmol/mol Mixture A, prepared in 2024, was analyzed against Mixture Y, prepared in 2025). $\Delta_{rel,i}$ is the relative deviation between the measured ($x_{i,obs}$) and the gravimetric (x_i) of the compound in the gravimetric gas mixture.

Since BAM produced sulfur gas standards for the first time in this study, no inventory standards were available to determine the consistency of preparation or accuracy. However, the cross-validation of the primary gas standards prepared by the two laboratories demonstrated the equivalence of these gas mixtures and enabled us to give a statement on their accuracy.

For the stability assessment, the set of primary gas standards was measured within various periods and verified against a new set produced in 2025 to obtain stability data for a period of approximately one year. BAM measured the multi-component gas mixtures in hydrogen (cylinder nos. 4130-250722 and 4135-250729, cf. Fig. S3, Part 2) that were freshly prepared approximately one year later against the argon standards (mixtures AA and BB). Since preliminary tests did not reveal any impact of matrix effects on the analysis (employing GC/SCD), hydrogen was used as matrix for this set. Due to time constraints within the project, no new binary H_2S mixtures could be prepared. However, a 1000 nmol/mol standard in hydrogen from 2022 was available and used to verify mixture CC.

2.6. Evaluation of the uncertainty

The combined and expanded relative uncertainty of each sulfur

compound of the gravimetric gas mixture ($u_{comb,i}$) is calculated following equations (6) and (7).

$$u_{comb,i} = \sqrt{u_{prep,i}^2 + u_{cons,i}^2 + u_{anal,i}^2} \quad (6)$$

$$U_i = k \cdot (u_{comb,i}) + z \quad (7)$$

The relative uncertainty due to preparation of the gas mixtures ($u_{prep,i}$) considers the uncertainty budgets for the weighing and the purity of the used chemicals; $u_{cons,i}$ is the relative uncertainty of the consistency of preparation and $u_{anal,i}$ is the relative uncertainty of analysis, which includes the uncertainty contributions from precision ($s_{R,i}$) and calibration ($u_{ref,i}$), respectively. The uncertainty due to the lack of accuracy ($\Delta_{rel,acc,i}$) or to instability of the sulfur compound in the gas mixture ($\Delta_{rel,stab,i}$) is the bias term z that is added (the largest absolute value of the two) to the other uncertainty contributions ($u_{comb,i}$) when the measured value deviates significantly from the gravimetric value [31]. This bias z represents possible losses (e.g. adsorption on contact material) and reactivity which are cylinder dependent and that cannot be assessed otherwise. The criterion for adding this bias is reported in equation (8).

$$|\Delta_{rel,i}| > 2 \cdot u_{comb,i} \quad (8)$$

where the absolute value of the relative deviation $\Delta_{rel,i}$ between $x_{i,obs}$, measured after preparation up to approximately one year life time of the gas mixture, and x_i is larger than the relative combined uncertainty of $u_{comb,i}$. The expanded uncertainty (U_i) of the sulfur compound in the gas mixture, reported in equation (7), is obtained by multiplying $u_{comb,i}$ complemented, where necessary, with the bias term z by a coverage factor k equal to 2, for a level of confidence of 95 %.

The uncertainty budgets of the dilution devices (section 2.3) are based on the measurement model of equations (1) and (2) and are calculated for the sulfur compounds close to the threshold value.

2.7. Cross-check validation

This part of our work compares the gravimetric gas standards prepared by BAM and VSL.

The cross-validation involved three parts.

1. Direct comparison of the high-fraction gas mixtures at 1000 nmol/mol using GC/SCD (no thermal desorption)
2. Direct comparison of the 100 nmol/mol gas mixtures using GC/SCD and/or TD-GC/SCD
3. Comparison of the 100 and/or 1000 nmol/mol gas mixtures diluted down to 4 nmol/mol by dynamic methods and analysis by TD-GC/SCD.

The cross-check validation was carried out independently at VSL and BAM facilities. For the evaluation, equations (4) and (5) were used. The results for each compound i in the gravimetric gas mixtures were expressed as the relative difference between BAM gas mixtures measured values ($x_{i,obs}$), obtained by direct comparison against VSL gas mixtures ($x_{i,ref}$) at the same amount fraction, and BAM gravimetric values (x_i).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Matrix effects

When performing the analysis of VSL and BAM gas mixtures via sample loop followed by direct injection into the GC at VSL, a matrix effect was noticeable, which led to slight differences in retention time (RT) and in the integrated GC peak areas. The effect on the retention time could be explained using hydrogen as GC carrier gas and the fact

that the samples in hydrogen (VSL mixtures) and argon (BAM mixtures) have significantly different velocities through the GC column. Furthermore, also the SCD detector appears to be influenced by the matrix of the gas mixtures. The pressure and flow requirements of the SCD burner base in combination with the relatively large sample volume injected (1000 μL) cause a deviation of ca. 2 % when the sample is in hydrogen or in argon. Note that this difference is smaller between mixtures in hydrogen and those in methane. When using the thermal desorber as injection system for the GC, only the sulfur analytes adsorb onto the sorbent trap. In addition, the MFC controlling the sample gas flow of the TD is calibrated for both hydrogen and argon. Therefore, no matrix effect is observed for the measurements of mixtures below 100 nmol/mol with TD-GC/SCD. This is also confirmed by VSL's cross-comparison results for H_2S : the deviations between the BAM and VSL mixtures measured by loop injection GC/SCD are larger than those by TD-GC/SCD.

When using the sample loop and direct injection into the GC at BAM, there was no indication of a matrix effect. For TD-GC/SCD, the MFC installed in the TD and calibrated to air by the manufacturer operates well provided that the matrix does not change. However, during the cross-check validation (sections 2.7 and 3.4) this condition caused a problem when the standards produced in argon and hydrogen were compared. Identical sampling flow settings led to different sampling volumes due to the different heat capacities of the two matrices.

3.2. Analytical precision and consistency of preparation

The repeatability ($s_{r,i}$) and the daily measurement standard deviations ($s_{A,i}$) of the gravimetric gas mixtures, H_2S binary and multi sulfurs, as well as the consistency of preparation, are reported in Tables 1 and 2.

The repeatability of the measurements of the sulfur compounds in hydrogen (VSL) is overall well below 1 %. The daily measurement variation is in most cases negligible compared to the repeatability results for the highest amount fraction, but it becomes significant for the lower amount fractions, particularly for H_2S at 10 nmol/mol, accounting for almost 5 times the repeatability value. These analytical precision results allow evaluation of the consistency of preparation of the gas mixtures, and they suggest that the relative differences among the gas mixtures, prepared at the same time, are in general within the measurement precision for the 10 and 100 nmol/mol and slightly higher for the 1000 nmol/mol. The significant deviations for H_2S and COS could be attributed to a combination of effects: high volatility and/or adsorption on the

Table 1

Measurement repeatability ($s_{r,i}$) and daily measurement relative standard deviations ($s_{A,i}$) of the sulfur compounds in the gravimetrically prepared gas mixtures in hydrogen and argon in the amount fraction range from 10 to 1000 nmol/mol. Measurements of 1000 nmol/mol are carried out with direct GC/SCD method, measurements of 10 and 100 nmol/mol with TD-GC/SCD method.

Compound name	1000 nmol/mol		100 nmol/mol		10 nmol/mol	
	$s_{r,i}$, %	$s_{A,i}$, %	$s_{r,i}$, %	$s_{A,i}$, %	$s_{r,i}$, %	$s_{A,i}$, %
Mixtures in hydrogen (VSL)						
H_2S	0.7	0.4	0.8	0.3	0.5	2.4
COS	0.7	0.1	0.7	1.0	0.6	1.3
MeSH	0.7	0.2	0.8	0.2	0.6	1.5
EtSH	0.6	0.2	0.7	0.7	0.8	2.0
DMS	0.7	0.1	0.6	1.5	0.5	0.7
DES	0.6	0.3	0.7	1.1	0.6	0.8
Mixtures in argon (BAM)						
H_2S	1.3	3.7	2.1	1.4		
COS	2.3	1.0	1.5	1.3		
MeSH	3.1	2.3	1.5	1.5		
EtSH	1.4	2.7	2.0	1.5		
DMS	1.8	1.1	1.1	1.7		
DES	3.3	1.3	0.6	0.9		
THT	1.6	1.1	2.6	1.3		

Table 2

Consistency of preparation of multi-component and binary sulfur gas mixtures in hydrogen in the amount fraction range from 10 to 1000 nmol/mol. The data are expressed as relative differences between the maximum ($RF_{\text{MAX},i}$) and minimum ($RF_{\text{MIN},i}$) response factors of each compound present in gas mixtures with same nominal amount fraction and prepared within the same period.

Compound name	1000 nmol/mol, Multi Mixtures A, B, C	100 nmol/mol, Multi Mixtures D, E	10 nmol/mol, Multi Mixtures G, H	1000 nmol/mol, Binary Mixtures L, M	100 nmol/mol, Binary Mixtures P, Q, R
	$RF_{\text{MAX},i} - RF_{\text{MIN},i}$, %				
H_2S	1.2	2.5	0.9	0.5	2.1
COS	4.5	0.2	<0.1		
MeSH	0.9	0.5	2.6		
EtSH	0.3	0.2	0.9		
DMS	0.8	0.6	1.6		
DES	1.0	0.9	0.9		

cylinder surfaces that could influence the preparation performance, closely proximate retention times on the GC that could affect the analytical separation, and consequently precision and quantification. It should be noted that the consistency of preparation of these gas mixtures at all ranges was estimated within one month from preparation and it covered gas mixtures prepared from different mother standards. Note that gas mixtures F and S were prepared at a later stage and therefore not included in the measurements. The consistency test for the 10 nmol/mol was performed with the gas mixtures prepared in differently coated cylinders (section 2.2.4). A test analysis immediately after preparation did not show a significant difference between them.

For the gas mixtures in argon (BAM), only ($s_{r,i}$) and ($s_{A,i}$) were determined for 1000 and 100 nmol/mol, but with THT included. The repeatability values are lower for the 100 nmol/mol standard measured with TD than for the 1000 nmol/mol mixture injected directly via the sample loop. This can be explained by the increased sensitivity achieved through the sample enrichment. This is also reflected in the daily measurement variance values. Apart from the values for H_2S and COS in the 1000 nmol/mol standards, where the difference between $s_{r,i}$ and $s_{R,i}$ is greatest, they are in the same order of magnitude for both amount fractions for the other substances.

3.3. Accuracy and stability

3.3.1. Gravimetric gas mixtures in hydrogen (VSL)

The accuracy of 3 multi-component mixtures at 1000 nmol/mol (mixtures A, B, C), was assessed in combination with the consistency test. Mixture A was further analyzed in 6 measurement campaigns to cover 1 to 12 months of gas mixture lifetime. Each measurement campaign was carried out at least twice. The results of the measurement of this mixture are represented in Fig. 4. The relative deviations ($\Delta_{\text{rel},i}$) of the measured values ($x_{i,\text{obs}}$) from the corresponding gravimetric values (x_i), obtained by using multi-component gas mixtures in methane as calibration standards, show a good agreement (<2 % $\Delta_{\text{rel},i}$) for all compounds with exception of EtSH. This component initially displays a significant loss after 75 days, after which the amount fraction remains approximately constant ($\Delta_{\text{rel},i}$ between -1.7 % and -3.5 %) (see Fig. 4). A similar trend, but within the 2 % relative variation, is visible for DMS. A direct comparison with a multi component mixture in hydrogen (mixture Y), freshly prepared one year later, shows that the relative deviation, expressed as $\Delta_{\text{rel,stab},i}$ (Table 3), is well within 2 %, confirming the stability results of the 1000 nmol/mol gas standard even for EtSH).

Two multi-components sulfur gas standards at 10 nmol/mol, mixtures G and H, prepared in two different cylinder types, were tested for accuracy and stability in 5 measurement periods to cover the 0 to 9 months mixture lifetime. The results of the measurements are presented

Mixture A - 1000 nmol/mol

Fig. 4. Graphical representation of the measurement of each compound of the multi sulfurs gas mixture at 1000 nmol/mol (Mixture A) within the period 33 to 388 days after sample preparation. The Y-axis is the relative deviation ($\Delta_{rel,i}$) of the measured from the gravimetric amount fraction; the error bars represent the relative uncertainty of the reported relative deviations ($k = 2$).

Table 3

Overview of the expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) of the gravimetric gas standards, multi-sulfurs and binary H_2S in hydrogen at 1000 nmol/mol (mixtures A, M), 100 nmol/mol (mixtures D, Q), and 10 nmol/mol (mixture G).

	$u_{prep,i}$, %	$u_{cons,i}$, %	$u_{anal,i}$, %		$u_{comb,i}$, %	mean $ \Delta_{rel,acc,i} $, %	$\Delta_{rel,stab,i}$, %	U_i ($k = 2$), %
			$s_{R,i}$	$u_{ref,i}$				
Multi-component gas mixture - 1000 nmol/mol								
H_2S	0.02	0.39	0.47	1.50	1.62	0.9	1.3	3.2
COS	0.05	1.49	0.32	1.50	2.14	1.1	1.3	4.3
MeSH	0.03	0.29	0.37	1.50	1.57	1.1	-1.4	3.1
EtSH	0.05	0.11	0.35	1.50	1.54	2.6	-1.8	3.1
DMS	0.05	0.28	0.29	1.50	1.55	1.4	-0.01	3.1
DES	0.02	0.33	0.38	1.50	1.58	1.6	0.02	3.2
Multi-component gas mixture - 100 nmol/mol								
H_2S	0.02	1.27	0.40	1.70	2.16	0.5	0.1	4.3
COS	0.05	0.10	1.02	2.17	2.40	0.2	-0.2	4.8
MeSH	0.03	0.23	0.39	1.64	1.70	0.55	-1.4	3.4
EtSH	0.05	0.11	0.73	1.97	2.11	1.8	-2.1	4.2
DMS	0.05	0.32	1.51	1.64	2.25	0.9	0.6	4.5
DES	0.03	0.44	1.13	1.64	2.04	1.1	1.2	4.1
Multi-component gas mixture - 10 nmol/mol								
H_2S	0.03	0.46	2.39	1.70	2.96	4.1	13.1	19.0
COS	0.05	0.01	1.34	2.17	2.55	2.4	-0.03	5.1
MeSH	0.04	1.29	1.54	1.64	2.60	2.6	-0.2	5.2
EtSH	0.05	0.43	2.01	1.97	2.85	3.3	-1.3	5.7
DMS	0.05	0.82	1.46	1.64	2.34	2.7	-1.3	4.7
DES	0.03	0.44	0.74	1.64	1.85	1.6	-0.8	3.7
H_2S binary gas mixture - 1000 nmol/mol								
H_2S	0.02	0.25	0.38	1.50	1.57	1.1	0.4	3.1
H_2S binary gas mixture - 1000 nmol/mol								
H_2S	0.02	0.68	0.63	1.70	1.94	1.8	1.9	4.0

in Fig. 5, while the relative deviations denoting the lack of accuracy ($|\Delta_{rel,acc,i}|$) and the possible instability ($\Delta_{rel,stab,i}$) are reported in Table 3. The relative deviations ($\Delta_{rel,i}$) of the measured values from the gravimetric ones, which were obtained using a 1000 nmol/mol gas standard dynamically diluted to the same amount fraction as calibration point, show that the two mixtures have different behaviors for H_2S , MeSH, and EtSH. However, before assessing the mixtures results, it must be noted that the last measurement period (258 days) has a positive relative deviation (bias) for most of the sulfur components. This effect is partly due to a change of the dynamic dilution set-up which influenced the accuracy of the calibration standard for the heaviest compounds (e.g. DES). The measurement data highlight that the cylinder type of mixture H (DB Gold, in orange) seems not to be suitable for these sulfur components: a significant loss of the mercaptans in time ($\sim 15\%$) and an increase of H_2S ($\sim 25\%$) of the gravimetric value is observed. On the contrary, the behavior of mixture G (Alpha Tech®, in blue), with an overall $\Delta_{rel,i} < 6$

%, with exception of H_2S , indicates that this type of cylinder is better suitable for producing gas standards for trace levels of sulfur components in hydrogen. The one-to-one measurements at 9-month lifetime of mixtures G and H, with the freshly prepared gravimetric mixtures J and K, shown in Table 3, confirm the increase of H_2S from the gravimetric value up to 13 % and 26 %, respectively. For DES, which seemed to increase at 258 days in Fig. 5, the one-to-one measurements show no significant deviations $\Delta_{rel,i} -0.8\%$ and -3.4% respectively), leading to the conclusion that there is sufficient stability of this compound in both cylinder types.

A similar behavior is visible for the multi-component gas mixtures at 100 nmol/mol, mixtures D and F, where the latter was prepared in the same cylinder type as mixture H (DB Gold). While mixture D has no appreciable instability after one year, even for H_2S , mixture F shows a loss of the two mercaptans ($\sim 7\%$) and an increase of H_2S ($\sim 23\%$).

The results of the measurement of the binary gas mixtures of H_2S in

Fig. 5. Graphical representation of the measurement of each compound of 2 multi-component sulfur gas mixtures at 10 nmol/mol (Mixture -G in blue and -H in orange) prepared in different cylinder types within the period 1 to 258 days after sample preparation. The Y-axis is the relative deviation ($\Delta_{rel,i}$) of the measured from the gravimetric amount fraction; the error bars represent the relative uncertainty of the reported relative deviations ($k = 2$). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

hydrogen at 1000 and 100 nmol/mol passed the criterion of equation (8), therefore proving sufficient accuracy and no significant instability after more than one year lifetime. Even the gas mixture at 100 nmol/mol, prepared in DB Gold cylinder type (mixture S), seems to remain stable, indicating that the effect visible on the multi component mixtures could be related to a reaction of the mercaptans to form H_2S , probably catalyzed by the cylinder surface.

3.3.2. Gravimetric gas mixtures in argon and hydrogen (BAM)

As mentioned in section 2.5, only statements on the stability of the mixtures in argon (mixtures AA and BB in Fig. 1), produced in 2024, compared to a freshly produced set in 2025 (cylinder nos. 4130-250722 and 4135-250729 in Fig. S3) can be made. Fig. 6 depicts the relative deviations $\Delta_{rel,i}$ of the 1000 nmol/mol and the 100 nmol/mol multi-sulfur gas standards. In both cases, a clear positive trend is apparent (blue columns). The deviations at the 1000 nmol/mol standard range between 2.5 % and 5.9 %, indicating a significant higher content in the old standard compared to the new one. In another calculation, DMS was used as an internal standard (orange columns), because it proved to be stable in the investigations (Section 3.3.1). Here, no clear trend appears and the deviations range between -2.2 % and 1.9 % which is a more plausible estimate. Comparing the 100 nmol/mol gas standards, significantly greater deviations and again a clear positive trend is observed. Since the TurboMatrix-TD could not be used due to the two different matrix gases, both mixtures were measured directly via the sample loop. The standard deviation of the repeated measurements ($N = 6$) was greater for the 100 nmol/mol (4 %–7 %) than for the 1000 nmol/mol standard (1 %–3 %) which is reflected by $\Delta_{rel,i}$ and most likely due to the sensitivity of the measurement. The volume of the sample loop is 250 μ L, a quarter of the volume of the corresponding VSL device. However, if DMS is also included as an internal standard here, $\Delta_{rel,i}$ of each compound of the 100 nmol/mol standard, at one year lifetime, are significantly reduced (-8.7 %–1.0 %). In conclusion, yet unidentified analytical issues appear that do not allow a clear statement to be made about the stability of all sulfurous components in the argon matrix. Using the internal standard, these could be at least partially compensated, indicating stability over at least one year.

Comparing the binary H_2S mixture (mixture CC in Fig. 1) with the older standard from 2022 in hydrogen, a $\Delta_{rel,i}$ of -1.5 % was obtained, indicating sufficient stability.

3.4. Cross-validation

Fig. 7 shows the results of the cross-validation carried out at VSL and BAM laboratories, respectively. The results are expressed, using equation (5), as relative difference ($\Delta_{rel,i}$) between BAM gas mixture measured and gravimetric values, using VSL gas mixture as reference. For the 4 nmol/mol level, only VSL results are shown. No evaluation was possible for BAM at this range due to the significant difference in sample volumes collected by the TurboMatrix TD. THT results are not presented, due to the unreliability of this compound in VSL gas standards.

In general, the relative deviation of the measurement of BAM gas standards from the gravimetric values remains well within 5 %, indicating the robustness of the analytical methods used by the two laboratories and an excellent degree of equivalence between BAM and VSL gas standards. Few exceptions are observed at 100 nmol/mol and 4 nmol/mol level. The largest deviation is obtained for H_2S at 100 nmol/mol in the multi sulfur mixture measured by BAM (negative deviation of about 22 %). Part of the explanation for this could be that the sensitivity of the direct GC/SCD measurement is significantly lower when measuring 100 nmol/mol than when measuring 1000 nmol/mol due to the relatively small sample loop of only 0.25 mL. However, this effect was only noticeable in the other compounds in terms of greater uncertainty of the relative deviations but not in terms of the average value for $\Delta_{rel,i}$.

3.5. Linearity of the analytical system in the range between 0.5 and 10 nmol/mol

In general, the linearity of the analytical systems used at BAM and VSL displays a first order linear behavior for the range between 0.5 and 10 nmol/mol for all sulfur components. The goodness-of-fit amounts to values between 0.8 and 1.9 for the analytical system at VSL and between 0.5 and 2.4 for that at BAM, respectively. A goodness-of-fit ≤ 2 indicates that the observed data fit well with the calculated model. For BAM's multi mix, however, this value exceeded 2.0 for H_2S , MeSH, and EtSH. Based on these data, a limit of detection (LoD) of ≤ 0.03 nmol/mol for both analytical systems was demonstrated. The standard deviation of the repeated measurements for the whole measurement range was between 0.9 and 1.8 % for VSL's system and between 1.1 and 4.2 % for the system at BAM, while the corresponding reproducibility standard deviation ($s_{R,i}$) was 1.8 to 3.3 % and 1.2 to 6.5 %, respectively. While at VSL all

Fig. 6. Graphical representation of the stability of each compound of 2 multi-sulfur gas mixtures at 1000 and 100 nmol/mol (Mixture prepared 2024 in Ar and 2025 in H₂). The Y-axis is the relative deviation ($\Delta_{rel,i}$) of the measured from the gravimetric amount fraction of each sulfur compound in the 2024 gas mixtures, using the 2025 ones as reference; the error bars represent the relative uncertainty of the reported relative deviations ($k = 2$).

sulfur components behaved similarly, for BAM measurements the largest dispersion of results was seen for the lighter compounds (e.g., H₂S, MeSH, EtSH).

3.6. Uncertainty of the gas standards

An overview of the expanded uncertainty of the gas standards prepared by gravimetry with the standard cylinder type is given in Tables 3 and 4. This uncertainty considers the contributions due to preparation, consistency, analysis, accuracy and stability effects up to 1 year for the 1000 and 100 nmol/mol and up to 9 months for the 10 nmol/mol gas standards. The standard uncertainty from gravimetric preparation ($u_{prep,i}$) is generally negligible [from 0.02 % to 0.05 % for hydrogen (VSL) and from 0.02 % to 0.31 % for argon standards (BAM)] in comparison to the other uncertainty sources. The largest uncertainty contribution is, the analytical precision ($u_{anal,i}$). In general, the uncertainty evaluation was properly assessed. However, for some species (e.g., H₂S at 10 nmol/mol), the resulting relative deviations obtained during the accuracy ($|\Delta_{rel,acc,i}|$) or the stability evaluations ($|\Delta_{rel,stab,i}|$), respectively, did not pass the criterion of equation (8) and therefore they were taken into account (bias z) and included to the total uncertainty.

For the mixtures in hydrogen prepared by VSL, the expanded

uncertainty of the 1000 nmol/mol gas standards, both multi and binary, ranges between 3.1 % and 4.3 %, for the 100 nmol/mol mixtures between 3.4 and 4.8 %, and for the multi-component sulfur mixture at 10 nmol/mol from 3.7 % to 5.7 %, with exception of H₂S, whose instability was the main contribution (13 %).

No values for ($u_{cons,iz}$) and ($u_{ref,i}$) are given for the argon mixtures (Table 4), as only one set of gas standards was produced, which is also why there is no statement on accuracy ($|\Delta_{rel,acc,i}|$) here. Instead, the contribution to instability was considered when $\Delta_{rel,stab,i}$ did not pass the criterion of equation (8). Due to the reasons discussed in section 3.3.2, the stability is presented with and without internal standard compensation (ISTD). With ISTD, the stability values decrease significantly and do not show a clear trend. Taking these values into account, the expanded uncertainty of the 1000 nmol/mol gas standards, both multi-components sulfur and binary H₂S, ranges between 2.2 % and 8.6 %, and for the 100 nmol/mol mixtures between 2.8 % and 5.1 %, respectively.

At VSL, the uncertainty calculation of the sulfur amount fractions obtained by dynamic dilution was based on the mathematical model given in equation (1). A typical standard uncertainty ($u_{comb,i}$) of 1.6 % was determined for the amount fraction of the sulfur components in the parent gas at 1000 nmol/mol (Table 3). For the gas flow rates, controlled by MFCs, a standard calibration uncertainty of 0.205 % was used, which

Fig. 7. Results of the cross-check validation at VSL (blue) and BAM (orange) laboratories. Data, expressed as relative deviation ($\Delta_{rel,i}$), compare BAM's PGS measured values against the gravimetric values, using VSL's standard as calibration reference for: a) the multi-sulfurs gravimetric standards at 1000 nmol/mol and 100 nmol/mol, and the dynamic standards at 4 nmol/mol, b) the H₂S binary standards at 1000 and 100 nmol/mol level (gravimetric) and the dynamic standard at 4 nmol/mol. The error bars represent the relative uncertainty of the reported relative deviations ($k = 2$). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

included the uncertainty of the primary calibrator (a mercury-sealed piston prover) and the repeatability of generating the flow rates. Table 5 shows the uncertainty budget calculated for a 10 nmol/mol H₂S (two-stage) dynamically generated standard gas mixture. The expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) is 3.4 % and it is mainly dominated by the parent gas mixture uncertainty. The expanded uncertainty calculated for the other sulfur compounds at amount fractions in the range 4 to 10 nmol/mol is similar, ranging between 3.4 % and 4.3 %.

Based on equation (2), the combined relative uncertainties for the dynamically generated gas standards in argon were calculated and are listed in Table 6. Since the standard uncertainty for the parent gas mixtures ($u_{prep,i}$) at 100 nmol/mol was taken for the calculations, both the combined relative uncertainties with and without usage of DMS as internal standard are given. They range from 3.1 % to 8 % (without ISTD) or 2.3 % to 3.2 % (with ISTD), respectively, for the 4 nmol/mol multi mix. The combined uncertainty for 4 nmol/mol of the H₂S binary mix was estimated with 2.9 %.

4. Conclusions

Highly accurate gaseous gravimetric primary reference materials for the determination of sulfur impurities in hydrogen at amount fractions of 100 nmol/mol and 1000 nmol/mol have been developed with hydrogen and argon as matrix gases with relative expanded uncertainties between 3 % and 9 % ($k = 2$) with 1 year stability and, additionally, at amount fractions of 10 nmol/mol in hydrogen with a relative expanded uncertainty between 4 % and 13 % ($k = 2$) with 9-month stability. Moreover, sulfur gas standards covering the range between 4 nmol/mol and 10 nmol/mol prepared by dynamic dilution have been validated with estimated relative uncertainty between 2.3 % and 4.3 %. These achievements outperform the requirements of ISO 21087, which specify relative standard uncertainties of up to 50 % for measurements of amount fractions of sulfur in hydrogen in regions below 10 nmol/mol. The performance of a cross-check study demonstrated that both standards are well comparable (≤ 5 % deviation for most of the sulfur species). Particular attention must be paid to the

Table 4

Overview of the expanded uncertainty U ($k = 2$) of the gravimetric gas standards, multi sulfurs and binary H_2S in argon at 1000 nmol/mol (mixtures AA, CC) and 100 nmol/mol (mixtures BB, DD) with and without internal standard (ISTD) compensation.

	$u_{prep,i}$, %	$s_{R,i}$, %	$u_{comb,i}$, %	$\Delta_{rel,stab,i}$, %	U_i ($k = 2$), %	$\Delta_{rel,stab,i}$ % (ISTD)	U_i ($k = 2$), % (ISTD)
Multi-component gas mixture - 1000 nmol/mol							
H_2S	0.31	4.3	4.3	5.0	8.6	1.7	8.6
COS	0.17	1.1	1.1	1.9	2.2	-1.2	2.2
MeSH	0.02	2.0	2.0	1.6	3.9	-1.5	3.9
EtSH	0.21	3.1	3.1	2.9	6.3	-0.2	6.3
DMS	0.19	0.8	0.8	4.2	4.2	-	
DES	0.14	1.5	1.5	5.3	5.3	1.1	3.0
THT	0.28	0.7	0.7	5.9	5.9	2.6	2.6
Multi-component gas mixture - 100 nmol/mol							
H_2S	0.31	1.0	1.0	4.8	4.8	4.6	4.6
COS	0.17	1.0	1.0	15.4	15.4	-5.1	5.1
MeSH	0.02	1.0	1.0	4.3	4.3	5.1	5.1
EtSH	0.21	1.1	1.1	13.4	13.4	-3.2	3.2
DMS	0.19	1.3	1.3	11.2	11.2		
DES	0.14	0.6	0.6	13.3	13.3	-3.1	3.1
THT	0.28	1.3	1.4	12.5	12.5	-2.4	2.8
H_2S binary gas mixture - 1000 nmol/mol							
H_2S	0.45	2.7	2.7	-1.5	5.5		
H_2S binary gas mixture - 100 nmol/mol							
H_2S	0.45	2.1	2.2	n/a	4.3		

Table 5

Uncertainty budget for the standards produced by VSL's dynamic dilution system determined for 10 nmol/mol H_2S in hydrogen.

Parameter	Value	Unit	Standard uncertainty	Distribution	Sensitivity coefficient	Contribution	
$x_{H_2S,prep}$	$1.011 \cdot 10^{-6}$	mol/mol	$1.62 \cdot 10^{-8}$	normal	$1.00 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.618 \cdot 10^{-10}$	89.82 %
$q_{analyte,F1}$	25.01	ml/min	0.07504	normal	$3.54 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.655 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.42 %
$q_{dilution,F1}$	174.99	ml/min	0.52498	normal	$-5.06 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2.655 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.42 %
$q_{analyte,F2}$	19.99	ml/min	0.05998	normal	$4.65 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$2.791 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.67 %
$q_{dilution,F2}$	229.98	ml/min	0.68993	normal	$-4.05 \cdot 10^{-11}$	$2.791 \cdot 10^{-11}$	2.67 %
$x_{H_2S,dil2}$	$10.11 \cdot 10^{-9}$	mol/mol	$1.71 \cdot 10^{-10}$	u_{comb,H_2S}			
		mol/mol	$3.42 \cdot 10^{-10}$	U_i ($k = 2$)			
			3.4 %	U_i ($k = 2$)			

Table 6

Uncertainty budget for the standards produced by BAM's dynamic dilution system at 4 nmol/mol of the multi mix in argon.

	Without ISTD (DMS)				With ISTD (DMS)			
	$u_{prep,i}$, %	$u_{q_{analyte,F1}}$, %	$u_{q_{dilution,F1}}$, %	U ($k = 2$), %	$u_{prep,i}$, %	$u_{q_{analyte,F1}}$, %	$u_{q_{dilution,F1}}$, %	U_i ($k = 2$), %
Multi-component gas mixture - 4 nmol/mol								
H_2S	2.4			3.1	2.3			3.0
COS	7.7			8.0	2.5			3.2
MeSH	2.1			2.9	2.5			3.2
EtSH	6.7	0.8	1.8	7.0	1.6	0.8	1.8	2.6
DMS	5.6			5.9				
DES	6.6			6.9	1.5			2.5
THT	6.2			6.5	1.2			2.3
H_2S binary gas mixture - 100 nmol/mol								
H_2S	2.2	0.8	1.8	2.9				

cylinder treatment. Comparing two treatments, significant losses of mercaptans (15 %) and increase of H_2S (25 %) were observed in one cylinder type, most likely caused by catalytical effects. For the same reason, all tubing and connectors used in the dynamic dilution system should be made from stainless steel and passivated also to minimize adsorption on the surfaces. All used MFCs must be calibrated to the respective matrix gases. This is of particular importance when gas standards prepared in different matrices are compared with each other.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Matthias Richter: Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Annarita Baldan:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Roel Beelen:** Writing –

review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ewoud J.J. de Boed:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Dirk Tuma:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Heinrich Kipphardt:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Olaf Wilke:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Formal analysis. **Adriaan M.H. van der Veen:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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